

Unlocking Lifelong Learning Through the Thai MOOC National Digital Learning Platform: A Case Study from Thailand

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Abstract. The Thailand Cyber University (TCU) project was founded under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research, and Innovation since 2005, to serve as the central platform for online education resources for Thai universities. This initiative enables institutions to develop and publish online courses that offer meaningful learning experiences. Since 2017, the Open edX platform has been adopted as the foundation for Thai MOOC to ensure accessibility and sustainability. Today, it supports a robust user base of over 2 million people and offers more than 750 courses. Over the years, TCU has enhanced its platform through three key initiatives like the effort to strengthen TCU's recognition as a global platform by fostering internal and international recognition and collaborations. Initiated a development of an AI-powered translation system to facilitate the localization of exchanged courses, making international content more accessible to Thai learners while also enabling Thai MOOC courses to reach a global audience. Finally, we are working towards establishing a national learning platform integrated with a credit bank system. Being a national platform, how does TCU plan ahead extend its reach beyond formal education, supporting lifelong learning for the general public and work-force development despite challenges that lie beyond? Looking ahead, TCU envisions a unified national online learning ecosystem. By integrating the "ThaiID" system across educational platforms and establishing a comprehensive credit bank. This initiative would not only support degree programs but also serve as a competency wallet for skill-based certifications, improving employability. Through continuous innovation and collaboration between academia, industry, and government, Thai MOOC strives to cultivate a robust and inclusive online education landscape, ensuring its relevance and long-term impact.

Keywords: MOOCs, a case study, online learning ecosystem, credit bank, lifelong learning, skill-based certifications,

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1 Introduction

1.1 Overview of Thai MOOC

From the founding of the Thailand Cyber University Project was established under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Development back in 2005. Serving as a central platform that provides knowledge related to technologies in teaching and supports higher education institutions in utilizing technologies in their teaching. Support and coordinate with higher education institutions in developing high quality online learning that are sustainable. To develop a central platform that will grant an opportunity to access education for all, the platform needs to be stable and able to support a large number of users and data. So, our project turns to Open edX platform and uses their open-source as a base line in developing Thai MOOC that we have today. As of the start since 2017, over two million learners are registered to Thai MOOC and 2,433,481 certificates have been issued with 750 courses offered on the platform as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Overview of Thai MOOC

1.2 Challenges and Initiatives

From our years of operations, we continue to diligently maintain, develop, and improve our platform. As online education and MOOCs continue growing globally, initiatives like Thai MOOC position Thailand well to meet increasing lifelong learning demands and upskill its population with in-demand competencies. The platform's open access model helps democratize educational opportunities for individuals across socioeconomic levels. Furthermore, its planned integration with a national credit bank system has the potential to create a comprehensive ecosystem for capturing and transferring learning achievements in both formal and informal settings as shown in

Figure 2. Recently we have utilized “ThaiID” by the Department of Provincial Administration, the Ministry of the Interior as an authentication method that is easy, secure, and reliable for the users. The issuing of certificates on Thai MOOC is also supported by the Ministry of Digital Economy and Society to build viability and trust on the certificate so learners are confident in them.

Fig.2. The national learning platform for lifelong learning.

Throughout its service, the Thailand Cyber University Project has faced challenges related to knowledge management, learner recognition, and learning habits in Thailand. To overcome these, TCU is implementing initiatives such as building collaborations, developing AI-powered translation tools, and establishing a national credit bank for MOOCs.

2 Thailand Cyber University: The Initiatives

From over a decade of its operation, TCU has been devoted to fostering higher education and online learning in Thailand for all [1]. There's many initiatives and projects that lay the groundwork for TCU to become what it is today with the Thai MOOC platform, offering access to online learning and becoming a place the public look for personal development. To move forward, there's also several ongoing project and mission that will lay the groundwork for TCU in the future with are:

2.1 Fostering internal and international recognition and collaborations

With rapid changes of global trends, it is important for ever growing institutions to form alliances, collaborate and have a partnership. This is crucial for any institution to

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be able to stay up to date through knowledge exchanges within their network and move forward together with their members. Thailand Cyber University project also follows these principles by having partnerships with many foreign institutions and being a part of an online learning alliance like the Global MOOC and Online Education Alliance, a group of a small but diverse number of universities and online learning platform providers that regularly have joint activities and annual conferences [2].

TCU regularly take parts at the annual conference of the alliance. For instance, in December 2024 TCU participated in the Global MOOC and Online Education Conference 2024 theme “Reimagining the Future of Higher Education in the Intelligence Era” Conference like this is a great chance for each institution to provide update on their ongoing project and built recognition among members of the alliance. During the conference there’s also held the “GMA Awards” where each member submitted their best courses from their platform which is a great way to showcase contents, built recognitions, and inspired one another. And to TCU’s horned, the course Coding for All – Smart Thinking in the Digital Era by Institute for the Promotion of Teaching Science and Technology which was recommend by Thai MOOC has won this award last year as shown in Figure 3. [2].

Fig.3. The GMA Awards Ceremony where the course Coding for All – Smart Thinking in the Digital Era won the awards with other members from the alliance.

TCU also held its own annual conference, the lasted one was held in August 2024 titled the 15th TCU International e-Learning Conference under the theme “Lifelong Learning Transformation: Entering the World of Artificial Intelligences in Education Era” as shown in Figure 4. With esteem speaker from all over the world ad our partner from ASEAN country and university in Thailand, this conference offers a stage for knowledge exchanges, progress update and showcase in while fostering collaborations between institutions both internal and internationals.

Fig.4. The opening ceremony of the 15th TCU International e-Learning Conference under the theme “Lifelong Learning Transformation: Entering the World of Artificial Intelligences in Education Era”

From learners' perspectives, there's also challenges in awareness and reconnection. Even with the above mention activity TCU conduct and promoted, many still have no idea what MOOC is and even with people who already know about it, do not see the point in using it or how it can be beneficial to them and how they can utilize it in real life. With this in mind, Thai MOOC organized a Thai MOOC Talk Spark program as shown in Figure 5 to promote the project. Broadcasting on Thai MOOC Facebook page TCU bringing instructors, academics, and professors that are behind the development of courses on Thai MOOC to share the behind the scene of the production, inviting learners that have successfully utilized what they have learned on Thai MOOC to share their insight to give other learners some ideas and inspirations [3].

Fig.5. All nine episodes of Thai MOOC Talk Spark in 2024 [3].

For over a decade, Thailand Cyber University (TCU) has championed online learning in Thailand, establishing the Thai MOOC platform for accessible personal development. To maintain its growth, TCU actively engages in global partnerships, participating in conferences and showcasing its content (e.g., the award-winning "Coding for All" course), and hosts its own annual conference to foster international collaboration [1]. Recognizing learner awareness challenges, TCU launched the Thai MOOC Talk Spark program to highlight course benefits and inspire potential users through success stories. These efforts aim to enhance TCU's visibility and establish it as a vital hub for lifelong learning [4].

2.2 Development of an AI-powered translation system

With the increase in number of collaborations with international partner comes challenges relate to languages barrier. Unlike collaborations between or with Thai University partner, the content exchanges are way less complicate since it is the same language. With foreign partner, language become one of the big challenges for TCU. Even if the courses were in English, when imported a selected of courses onto Thai MOOC the accessibility of them is still limited since not all of the learners understand English.

Despite the availability of excellent educational content, language barriers hinder learners' comprehension and engagement, leading to a loss of educational opportunities from quality learning resources. Recognizing the significance of learners' language challenges on the Thai MOOC Platform, the Thailand Cyber University Project has deemed it appropriate to undertake a research and development project the Research and Development Project on AI-Powered Language Translation for the Thai MOOC Platform with Assoc. Prof. Prakob Koraneekij from the Department of Educational Technology and Communications, Chulalongkorn University. The objective is to integrate artificial intelligence (AI) and digital language translation technologies into the services provided to learners on the Thai MOOC Platform, thereby enabling learners to access up-to-date knowledge and keep pace with global changes equitably. The project was recently showcase at "MOOCs, Micro-Credentials, and Digital Badges for Lifelong Learning in Higher Education: A Collaborative Exchange Between Thai MOOC and JMOOC" Thai MOOC and JMOOC Workshop in February 2025 to give a demonstration of its process and how it works as shown in Figure 6. [4], [5], [6], [7].

Fig.6. The process of AI-Powered Language Translation that was showed case.

To overcome language barriers on the Thai MOOC platform, TCU is developing an AI-powered translation project. This initiative will localize international courses, increasing accessibility for Thai learners and maximizing the benefits of foreign partnerships. By addressing language challenges, TCU broadens its reach and enables learners to engage with global knowledge.

2.3 Working towards establishing a national learning platform

One of TCU current main goals is to create an ecosystem for online education and build a national catalog that compiles all the courses from other universities or organizations to help facilitate learners when they looking for what they want to learn. Currently, there's some difficulty from the fact that all the courses are in different platforms of each organization they belong to and learners have to make a different account in order to enroll. After seeing how useful the ThaiID app is, TCU came to the idea that if every platform in Thailand utilizes this app it will help learners access different courses on different platforms easier and secure. With all of these elements we can cooperate with the credit bank system and become a true national platform.

Able to be a competency wallet that other than accumulating credit for receiving a degree, it also can be a place that stores skill-based certifications which can help with job finding. Since nowadays employers aren't just looking for someone with one pacific knowledge and specialty, they are now looking for someone who is well rounded, equipped with both academic knowledge and social skills, able to socialize and work in a team. This opened an opportunity for instructors, academics, and professors from various universities around Thailand to develop a diverse range of courses to provide learners with various knowledge to choose. Other than that, having a national platform

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is also a great place for teachers and professors to choose online courses on the platform to be a part of their curriculum, which can foster an academic collaboration between institutions also [8], [9], [10].

To bring this vision to reality, TCU has been regularly discussing with regional higher education universities network for the implementation plans and the standardizations of the learning outcome in order to fully and efficiently utilize the central credit bank system. Lead by Prof. Dr. Supachai Pathumnakul, Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation, in February 2025, A discussion forum was held to outline a guideline for advanced learning and credit transfer between institutions through online learning, to provide learners with diverse learning options and reduce study time as shown in Figure 7. The meeting aimed to discuss hybrid education combining online and on-site learning, joint education programs among multiple universities, guidelines for online course delivery (via Thai MOOC or university MOOC platforms) with systematic online course assessment, and guidelines for degree conferral upon graduation, allowing students to receive degrees from a designated higher education institution as agreed upon.

Fig.7. Discussion forum lead by Prof. Dr. Supachai Pathumnakul, Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation on the guideline for advanced learning and credit transfer between institutions through online learning.

TCU aims to establish a unified national online education ecosystem with a central course catalog, ThaiID integration, and a competency wallet. This platform will enhance employability, foster academic collaboration by standardizing learning outcomes with regional universities, and benefit both learners and institutions by providing diverse options and expanding educational reach.

3 Conclusion

The Thailand Cyber University Project (TCU) has significantly advanced online education in Thailand through various initiatives and recognition of challenges. Over the past decade, TCU has focused on key areas: enhancing global recognition,

improving accessibility through AI-powered translation, and developing a unified national learning platform. To strengthen its global presence, TCU has been actively building collaborations with international institutions. This effort aims to elevate the standard of online courses and expand the platform's reach. TCU has also been proactive in localizing international content for Thai learners by developing an AI-powered translation system. This initiative not only makes global educational resources more accessible but also enables Thai MOOC courses to reach a wider, international audience. TCU is also in the process of creating a national learning platform that integrates a credit bank system. This platform will allow learners to accumulate and transfer credits across different institutions, streamlining the educational experience. Additionally, it will function as a competency wallet, storing skill-based certifications to enhance employability. Despite these advancements, many challenges such as changing traditional learning habits and promoting self-directed learning still unable to be completely tackled. There are also issues with disparities in digital access and readiness, which affect the widespread adoption of online learning. Furthermore, there's still need to constantly come up with new and engaging ways to raise public awareness about the benefits of MOOCs, as many potential learners are still unaware of these resources.

In summary, TCU has made substantial progress in establishing a robust online education framework. Through strategic collaborations, technological advancements, and forward-thinking initiatives, it is paving the way for a more inclusive and dynamic learning environment in Thailand.

4 References

- [1] Thammetar, T., Theeraroungchaisri, A., Khlaisang, J., Duangchinda, V.: The Genesis and Theoretical Underpinnings of Thai MOOC : Promoting Lifelong Learning in Thailand. In: 2024 Trend Report Higher Education and e-Learning in ASEAN - Volume 1, 1st edn., vol. 1, pp. 30–38 (2024). [EBook, Online]. Available from: <http://www.aseanoer.net/notice/doNoticeSelect.acu?page=1¬iceSeqno=100&dateOrder=Y&dateOrderSort=desc&viewOrder=N&viewOrderSort=desc&searchCondition=1&searchKeyword=#>, last accessed 2025/05/01
- [2] Global MOOC and Online Education Alliance: Announcement of Winners for 2024 GMA Awards (2025). <https://mooc.global/gma-secretariat/announcement-of-winners-for-2024-gma-awards/>, last accessed 2025/03/07
- [3] ThaiMOOC: Thai MOOC Talk Spark EP 9: Law for the People (2024). <https://www.facebook.com/ThaiMOOC/videos/584326327516079/?mibextid=rS40aB7S9Ucbxw6v>, last accessed 2025/03/07
- [4] ThaiMOOC: MOOCs, Micro-Credentials, and Digital Badges for Lifelong Learning in Higher Education: A Collaborative Exchange Between Thai MOOC and JMOOC” Thai MOOC and JMOOC Workshop (2025).

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https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rqm4F97nSWI&list=PLmEnIQ-_8_NAKdXOUwX7CtGpM_yXJ2Ue5, last accessed 2025/03/07

- [5] Serth, S., Staubitz, T., van Elten, M., Meinel, C.: Measuring the effects of course modularizations in online courses for life-long learners. *Front. Educ.* 7, Article 1008545 (2022). doi:10.3389/educ.2022.1008545
- [6] Wathanakom, N., Thammetar, T., Theeraroungchaisri, A., Khlaisang, J., Duangchinda, V.: Revitalizing Thai MOOC brand: A Journey to Launch a line extension of Thai MOOC Academy with Distinctive Brand Positioning and Integrated Communications in Thailand. In: 2023 Trend Report: ACU Secretariat (ASEAN Cyber University Secretariat), Higher Education and e-Learning in ASEAN - Volume 1 (2023). [Online]
- [7] Knowledge Network Institute of Thailand: Knowledge Hub Discussion #18" CYBER University 2025" (2025). <https://fb.watch/yalbuADF6v/?mibextid=rS40aB7S9Ucbxw6v>, last accessed 2025/03/07
- [8] Theeraroungchaisri, A., Khlaisang, J., Duangchinda, V., Thammetar, T.: Thai MOOC : Elderly Care MOOC, A Series of Skill Based MOOC. In: 2022 Trend Report : ACU Secretariat (ASEAN Cyber University Secretariat), Higher Education and e-Learning in ASEAN - Volume 2, pp. 26-34 (2022). [Online]. Available from: <http://www.aseanoer.net/notice/doNoticeSelect.acu?noticeSeqno=28#>, last accessed 2025/05/01
- [9] Boonlue, T., Tsoi, K.: The Integration of Thai MOOCs for Enhancing Lifelong Learning in Thailand. *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies.* 19, 1, 64–78 (2021).
- [10] Khlaisang, J., Duangchinda, V., Thammetar, T., Theeraroungchaisri, A.: Work-Based Skills Courses in Thai MOOC. In: 2022 Trend Report : ACU Secretariat (ASEAN Cyber University Secretariat), Higher Education and e-Learning in ASEAN - Volume 3, pp. 24-32 (2022). [Online]. Available from: <http://www.aseanoer.net/notice/doNoticeSelect.acu?noticeSeqno=48#>, last accessed 2025/05/01